

**MATHEMATICAL MODELLING OF DECISION MAKING: THE CASE
OF EDUCATIONAL AND EMPLOYMENT CHOICES IN GHANA**

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Abstract

The Ising model is used as a model for decision making involving social interaction and generalises socio-economic discrete choice model. This model is of a mean-field type as each individual interact with the rest of the individuals. In this work we study how educational and employment choices is influenced by social attributes of gender and residence. The estimation procedure of [14] is used to estimate both the social and private incentive parameters of the model. The current work differ from that in [14] in two regards: (a) population is divided into subgroups according to socio-economic attributes with unequal subgroup sizes and (b) different attributes values are considered. From the estimates place of residence seems to have significant effect on the type of employment and educational choices an individual makes than gender.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Education provides people with the knowledge and skills that can lead to better employment opportunities and a better quality of life. The educational level attained by an individual explicitly determines the occupational choice of that individual. All these attainments and choices of individuals are made under certain conditions or influences and interactions from peers, neighbours and family members. These conditions may include, the wealth quintile of the individual, gender and where the individual resides. Those who reside in the rural areas with the poorest wealth quintile are more likely to have no education. The type of occupational choices made by individuals varies greatly by gender. The leading occupation among women in Ghana is sales and services, which employs more than half of women [1]. Other occupations in which women are engaged include agriculture, skilled manual labour, professional, technical, or managerial work, and unskilled manual labour and clerical positions. Place of residence has a significant effect on these types of occupation. As expected, a high proportion of individuals in rural areas, are engaged in agricultural work. Urban women are more likely to be engaged in sales and services, while urban men are more likely to be engaged in skilled manual labour [1].

In this thesis we will consider how the collective behaviour of individuals are being influenced by their gender and place of residence, when it comes to their choices of educational attainment and employment.

We are interested in: 1) how the two attribute (of gender and residence) are distributed among groups in a population and 2) how different subgroups influence each other.

We start with assumptions about how individuals may change their decisions and behaviours as a consequence of social interactions, and then derive the population-level consequences of such assumptions using tools from statistical physics.

In particular, collective behaviours are among the most commonly observed ways of self-organization in biology, ecology and socio-economics [2, 3, 4]. Existence of collective behaviours has been proven for some classes of mean field spin systems derived as classical reversible ferromagnetic models by adding a dissipation term [5, 6]. The simplest spin system within this class is the mean field Ising model proposed in [5]. Models based on mean field interacting spin systems, are able to show a good qualitative description of behaviour of a large group or population in any well organised systems. Due to this reason and their analytical tractability, they have also been applied in social sciences [7], finance [8], chemistry [9] and ecology [10]. An interesting family, which has naturally emerged in applications, is a multi species extension of the mean field Ising model. The possibility of taking account for several kinds of magnetic spins is a peculiar feature that may be relevant to capture diverse phenomena from magnetism in anisotropic materials to social issues [11].

A simple statistical mechanical model based on binary units was first explored by Ising (1925) (following an idea of his supervisor, Lenz), in the context of ferromagnetism. We have chosen to name our model the mean field Ising model to make the formal and historical link with statistical physics more explicit. Many of the tools we use in this

thesis have been developed in this branch of physics and it will be discussed in the next section.

The Mean-field Ising Model (Curie-Weiss Model)

A major topic of interest in statistical mechanics and in physics in general is the understanding of phase transitions which requires the study of interacting models. Phase transition in a physical system corresponds to a change from one phase (behaviour) of the physical system to another through changes in the environment of the system such as freezing of water to form ice. The Ising model named after the physicist Ernst Ising, is a mathematical model for ferromagnetism in statistical mechanics [16]. This model for ferromagnetism was developed in 1924 by Professor Wilhelm Lenz and his graduate student Ernst Ising. The original motivation for the model was to explain the phenomenon of ferromagnetism. Iron exhibits magnetic properties once it is magnetised, it was clear that magnetism should be due to a large number of moving electrons. The Ising model was designed to investigate whether a large fraction of the electrons could be made to spin in the same direction using only local forces [16]. In the Ising model, we consider a lattice of magnetic moments, on each lattice site, the local magnetic moment is represented by a spin. We assume that the spin has just two possible states, either pointing up or pointing down. Mathematically, we represent the spin at site i by the variable $\sigma_i = \pm 1$. In this notation, $+1$ means that the spin is pointing up, and -1 means that it is pointing down. The Ising model is made up of an energy function (Hamiltonian) that assigns interaction energies to spin configurations. This energy function takes the form:

$$H_N(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i,l=1}^N J_{il} \sigma_i \sigma_l + \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \sigma_i. \quad (1.1)$$

The energy function for the Ising model consists of two contributions; namely the interaction between neighbouring spins and the effect of an applied magnetic field on each individual spin. The interaction between neighbouring spins tends to induce parallel alignment of the neighbours, so it should be favourable when the neighbours are both +1 or both -1, and unfavourable when the neighbours are +1 next to -1. Hence, for each pair of neighbours i and l , the interaction energy is given by $J_{il}\sigma_i\sigma_l$, where J_{il} is a positive coefficient giving the interaction strength between spins at i and l . The parameter h_i is the external magnetic field applied to site i . If the magnetic field h_i is pointing up, it favours spins pointing up; if the field is pointing down, it favours spins pointing down. Hence, for each site i , the external field contributes to the energy function by a term of $h_i\sigma_i$ [24]. This model is of a mean-field type as each spin interacts with the rest of the spins. The effect of all the other spins on any given spin is approximated by the average effect of the rest, thus reducing a many-body problem to a one-body problem which makes computations easy.

In this thesis we will use the Ising model to model discrete choice problem namely choice for educational attainment and occupation, following the work of [19].

Chapter 2

Theoretical Model

Individual decisions or choices can be influenced once there is a large number of people interacting with the individual concerning a choice or decision. Each individual in a population of N agents chooses a binary action, such as choosing YES or NO on some issue at some common time. Each of these binary actions is coded into σ_i with

$$\sigma_i = \begin{cases} +1, & \text{if individual } i \text{ choses YES} \\ -1, & \text{if individual } i \text{ choses NO} \end{cases}$$

for $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. We now define the Ising energy function H_N for any $\sigma \in \Omega_N = \{-1, +1\}^N$ as

$$H_N(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i,l=1}^N J_{il} \sigma_i \sigma_l + \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \sigma_i. \quad (2.1)$$

Here σ_i is the choice of individual i , J_{il} is the interaction strength or coefficient of interaction between individual i and l and h_i is the external field of influence. The function H_N on the configuration σ is called the Hamiltonian/energy function of the model which represent the utility of individuals as a result of their choices and the influences on them while making a decision [23]. The function H_N in statistical mechanics usually arise from a system's physical properties [15]. In our case $H_N(\sigma)$ returns the level of

satisfaction of the entire population for making the choice σ . The higher the $H_N(\sigma)$ the higher the level of satisfaction of the population. It can also be considered as the utility of the population. It has two parts, the first part models the social incentive of individuals in the population and the second part models the private incentive of an individual. J_{il} measures the influence an individual i has on individual l and also is the strength of individuals social incentive so whenever J_{il} is positive it means conformity or imitation is rewarded and when J_{il} is negative it means imitation or conformity is not rewarded.

2.1 Discrete Choice

Our interest now is how to model the private incentive h_i of an individual. In order to do that we will consider only private incentive for now by ignoring interactions i.e. we put $J_{il} \equiv 0$ for every $i, l \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, where N is the total number of individuals in the population. Our general utility function now becomes

$$H_N(\sigma) = \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \sigma_i. \quad (2.2)$$

Each individual will be assigned to a vector of socio-economic attribute a_i and each component of the vector is a binary variable and takes a value of 1 or 0 [14]. Since each individual has his or her own distinct socio-economical attribute, we will let a_i be defined for $i = \{1, \dots, N\}$ as follows

$$a_i = (a_i^{(1)}, a_i^{(2)}, \dots, a_i^{(k)})$$

where the $a_i^{(j)}$'s are $\{0,1\}$ - valued. For instance consider the case where the attributes of interest are level of education $a_i^{(1)}$ and gender $a_i^{(2)}$ with

$$a_i^{(1)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if individual } i \text{ is literate} \\ 0, & \text{if individual } i \text{ is illiterate} \end{cases}$$

and

$$a_i^{(2)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if an individual } i \text{ is a Female} \\ 0, & \text{if an individual } i \text{ is a Male} \end{cases}$$

If the value of an attribute is zero for an individual then it means that particular attribute does not contribute to the private incentive of that individual. Because h_i is what motivate an individual to make a choice or decision it is reasonable for it to become dependent on the vector of socio-economic attribute a_i since every rational person considers his or her status before making a choice or decision. Therefore it can be written as the function of a_i as follows: let α_j for $j = 0, \dots, k$, be the component of vector $\alpha = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k)$ and assume α_j does not depend on the specific individual i . The vector α tells us the relative weight or the importance that the various socio-economic attribute have or measures the private incentive for each attribute when an individual is making a decision. In our case this leads to

$$h_i = \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j a_i^{(j)} + \alpha_0. \quad (2.3)$$

Here α_0 is the base private incentive every individual has, regardless of their individual socio-economic attribute. It follows from [15] that the probability of an individual i with attribute a_i deciding on “YES” is given by

$$P(\sigma_i = 1) = \frac{e^{h_i}}{e^{h_i} + e^{-h_i}}. \quad (2.4)$$

2.2 Interaction

The global behaviour of large groups of people may change due to some slight variations in the social structure of the group. For instance a change in the pronunciation of a language due to a small immigrant population, or a substantial

decrease in crime rate as a result of actions taking by the authorities [20, 18]. From statistical mechanics point of view, these abrupt transition may be considered as phase transition caused by the interaction between individuals. In this section we will focus on finding a suitable parametrisation for the interaction coefficient J_{il} and a systematic procedure that allows us to estimate the parameters characterizing the model from data. From our discrete choice model each individual i is assigned to k socio-economic attribute

$$a_i = (a_i^{(1)}, a_i^{(2)}, \dots, a_i^{(k)}), \quad \text{with } a_i^{(j)} \in \{0,1\}$$

Thus $a_i \in \{0,1\}^k$. Therefore the population of size N can be partitioned into 2^k groups that do not overlap. Each of the groups is identified by one of the elements of $\{0,1\}^k$. Let I_{N_g} be the set of individuals in partition g for $g = 1, \dots, 2^k$ and $|I_{N_g}| = N_g$. Therefore $N = N_1 + \dots + N_{2^k}$. Let $I_N = \{1, 2, \dots, N\} = \bigcup_{g=1}^{2^k} I_{N_g}$ with $I_{N_g} \cap I_{N_{g'}} = \emptyset$, for $g \neq g'$.

Individuals in the same group or partition are characterised by the same socio-economic attribute or individuals with the same socio-economic attributes are characterised as a group or partition. Therefore it follows from equation (2.3) that all individuals in a partition or a group g have the same private incentive h_g .

In what follows we will assume that for any pair of groups g and g' $J_{il} = \bar{J}_{gg'}$ for every $i \in I_{N_g}$ and $l \in I_{N_{g'}}$. It follows from this assumption and equation (2.1) that

$$H_N(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \sum_{g'=1}^{2^k} \left(\sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sum_{l \in I_{N_{g'}}} J_{il} \sigma_i \sigma_l \right) + \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} h_i \sigma_i. \quad (2.5)$$

The private incentive part then becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} h_i \sigma_i &= \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \frac{N_g}{N_g} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} h_i \sigma_i \\
&= \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} N_g \frac{h_g}{N_g} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i \\
&= \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} N_g h_g \hat{m}_g
\end{aligned}$$

In the second equality we use that $h_i = h_g$ for every $i \in I_{N_g}$. Note that

$$\hat{m}_g = \frac{1}{N_g} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i, \quad (2.6)$$

is the average decision for the individuals in group or partition g .

Again the term in the bracket of the first term in equation (2.5) becomes;

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sum_{l \in I_{N_{g'}}} J_{il} \sigma_i \sigma_l &= \frac{N_g}{N_g} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i \frac{N_{g'}}{N_{g'}} \sum_{l \in I_{N_{g'}}} J_{il} \sigma_l \\
&= \bar{J}_{gg'} N_g \left(\frac{1}{N_g} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i \right) N_{g'} \left(\frac{1}{N_{g'}} \sum_{l \in I_{N_{g'}}} \sigma_l \right), \\
&= \bar{J}_{gg'} N_g N_{g'} \hat{m}_g \hat{m}_{g'}.
\end{aligned}$$

The second equality uses that $J_{il} = \bar{J}_{gg'}$ for every $i \in I_{N_g}$ and $l \in I_{N_{g'}}$.

Now from equation (2.5) we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
H_N(\sigma) &= \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \sum_{g'=1}^{2^k} \bar{J}_{gg'} N_g \hat{m}_g N_{g'} \hat{m}_{g'} + \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} h_g N_g \hat{m}_g \\
&= \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \sum_{g'=1}^{2^k} \bar{J}_{gg'} \frac{N}{N} N_g \hat{m}_g \frac{N}{N} N_{g'} \hat{m}_{g'} + \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} h_g \frac{N}{N} N_g \hat{m}_g \\
&= N \left[\sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \sum_{g'=1}^{2^k} \frac{\bar{J}_{gg'}}{2} \frac{N_g}{N} \hat{m}_g \frac{N_{g'}}{N} \hat{m}_{g'} + \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} h_g \frac{N_g}{N} \hat{m}_g \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Let $m_g = \frac{N_g}{N} \hat{m}_g$, $m_{g'} = \frac{N_{g'}}{N} \hat{m}_{g'}$ and $J_{gg'} = \frac{\bar{J}_{gg'}}{2}$, where $\frac{N_g}{N}$ and $\frac{N_{g'}}{N}$ are the relative sizes of groups I_{N_g} and $I_{N_{g'}}$ respectively. Hence m_g and $m_{g'}$ are the weighted average decision of the individuals in groups g and g' respectively.

Our model has now been changed from individual choices to group choices or decision, hence our general Hamiltonian now becomes;

$$H_N(\sigma) = N \left[\sum_{g=1}^{2^k} \sum_{g'=1}^{2^k} J_{gg'} m_g m_{g'} + \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} h_g m_g \right] \quad (2.7)$$

Now H_N returns the level of satisfaction for the entire population. $J_{gg'}$ measures the influence group g has on group g' and also is the social incentive of group g and g' which when positive means the groups are satisfied with same choices (either both positive or negative) and when negative group imitation is not encouraged or rewarding and h_g is the private incentive of the group g .

In this work we will consider using two attributes gender and residence, which implies our number of socio-economic attribute is $k = 2$ and we will have 4 partitions

as each attribute assumes two values. We will look at how ones gender (either male or female) and residence (either urban or rural) affect his or her choices concerning education and employment.

The Hamiltonian (2.9) now becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
H_N(\sigma) &= N \left[\sum_{g=1}^4 \sum_{g'=1}^4 J_{gg'} m_g m_{g'} + \sum_{g=1}^4 h_g m_g \right] \\
&= N \sum_{g=1}^4 m_g \left[\sum_{g'=1}^4 J_{gg'} m_{g'} + h_g \right] \\
&= N [U_1 m_1 + U_2 m_2 + U_3 m_2 + U_4 m_4],
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$U_1 = J_{11}m_1 + J_{12}m_2 + J_{13}m_3 + J_{14}m_4 + h_1,$$

$$U_2 = J_{21}m_1 + J_{22}m_2 + J_{23}m_3 + J_{24}m_4 + h_2,$$

$$U_3 = J_{31}m_1 + J_{32}m_2 + J_{33}m_3 + J_{34}m_4 + h_3,$$

$$U_4 = J_{41}m_1 + J_{42}m_2 + J_{43}m_3 + J_{44}m_4 + h_4.$$

Generally

$$U_g = \sum_{g'=1}^{2^k} J_{gg'} m_{g'} + h_g, \quad (2.8)$$

for any number of attribute k chosen and $g = 1, \dots, 2^k$.

Individuals are differentiated by their mutual interactions: there are four intra-group interactions ($J_{11}, J_{22}, J_{33}, J_{44}$), tuning how strongly individuals in the same group imitate each other, and twelve inter-group interactions ($J_{12}, J_{21}, J_{13}, J_{31}, J_{14}, J_{41}, J_{23}, J_{32}, J_{24}, J_{42}, J_{34}, J_{43}$), giving the magnitude of the imitation between individuals from dis-

tinct groups.

Below is a schematic representation of the interaction network if we were to use only one attribute.

Figure 2.1: A schematic representation of the interaction network for an interacting model. Individuals are divided into two populations I_1 and I_2 . Within I_1 (resp. I_2) individuals feel a mean field interaction with coupling J_{11} (resp. J_{22}). Besides, population I_1 (resp. I_2) influences the dynamics of the other group through its magnetization with strength J_{12} (resp. J_{21}). Figure taken from [12].

In [13] the case $k = 1$ of this model was considered: the model's thermodynamic limit was proved, and it was given a rigorous derivation of the model's solution, as well as an analysis of some of its properties. In particular, it was shown there that the model factorizes completely, so that all the information about the equilibrium states of the model is captured by the self-consistent equations [14]:

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{m}_1 &= \tanh(J_{11}\bar{m}_1 + J_{12}\bar{m}_2 + J_{13}\bar{m}_3 + J_{14}\bar{m}_4 + h_1) = \tanh(U_1) \\ \bar{m}_2 &= \tanh(J_{21}\bar{m}_1 + J_{22}\bar{m}_2 + J_{23}\bar{m}_3 + J_{24}\bar{m}_4 + h_2) = \tanh(U_2) \\ \bar{m}_3 &= \tanh(J_{31}\bar{m}_1 + J_{32}\bar{m}_2 + J_{33}\bar{m}_3 + J_{34}\bar{m}_4 + h_3) = \tanh(U_3) \\ \bar{m}_4 &= \tanh(J_{41}\bar{m}_1 + J_{42}\bar{m}_2 + J_{43}\bar{m}_3 + J_{44}\bar{m}_4 + h_4) = \tanh(U_4)\end{aligned}$$

This allows us, in particular, to write the probability of individual i making a decision, if i belongs to group g in a closed form, similar to equation (2.4) as

$$P(\sigma_i) = \frac{e^{\sigma_i U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}}, \quad (2.9)$$

where $\sigma_i \in \{-1, +1\}$

Probability of i deciding on $\sigma_i = 1$ is

$$P(\sigma_i = 1) = \frac{e^{U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}}$$

and that of $\sigma_i = -1$ is

$$P(\sigma_i = -1) = \frac{e^{-U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}}$$

Let E be the expectation of σ_i for all i in g . Then

$$E(\sigma_i) = \frac{(1)e^{U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}} + \frac{(-1)e^{-U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}}$$

$$E(\sigma_i) = \bar{m}_g = \frac{e^{U_g} - e^{-U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}} = \frac{2}{2} \left(\frac{e^{U_g} - e^{-U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}} \right)$$

$$\text{Therefore } \bar{m}_g = \tanh(U_g)$$

where \bar{m}_g is the expected average decision level for every $g = 1, \dots, 4$.

In our case where $k = 2$, the general expression for the U_g takes the form

$$U_g = \sum_{g'=1}^4 J_{gg'} \bar{m}_{g'} + h_g. \quad (2.10)$$

This is a linear regression model and the utility of a group with respect to the parameters $J_{gg'}$ and α_j 's. Note that

$$h_g = \sum_{j=1}^2 \alpha_j a_g^{(j)} + \alpha_0.$$

This is the basic quantity needed to estimate the interacting model starting from real

data. Here $J_{gg'}$, α_j , and α_0 are the parameters to be estimated.

In the case where $J_{gg'} = 0$ for every g, g' we get the non-interacting version of the model given in equation (2.2) of Section 2.1. Similarly, we could write the non-interacting Hamiltonian as

$$H_N(\sigma) = N \sum_{g=1}^{2^k} h_g m_g. \quad (2.11)$$

This reduces to the following in our case where $k = 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} H_N(\sigma) &= N [h_1 m_1 + h_2 m_2 + h_3 m_3 + h_4 m_4] \\ &= N [U_1 m_1 + U_2 m_2 + U_3 m_3 + U_4 m_4] \end{aligned}$$

where $U_1 = h_1$, $U_2 = h_2$, $U_3 = h_3$, $U_4 = h_4$. Hence we can say that $U_g = h_g$ for $g = 1, \dots, 4$.

The non interacting model also factorises completely to produce these equilibrium weighted average choice:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{m}_1 &= \tanh U_1 \\ \bar{m}_2 &= \tanh U_2 \\ \bar{m}_3 &= \tanh U_3 \\ \bar{m}_4 &= \tanh U_4. \end{aligned}$$

Here $U_g = h_g$. This will be the main tool that we will use to estimate the non-interacting models parameters starting from real statistical data.

2.3 Estimation

From the model an individual i belonging to group g has the probability of choosing 1 being equals to

$$P(\sigma_i = 1) = \frac{e^{U_g}}{e^{U_g} + e^{-U_g}},$$

where

$$U_g = \sum_{g'=1}^4 J_{gg'} m_{g'} + h_g$$

and

$$h_g = \sum_{j=1}^2 \alpha_j a_g^{(j)} + \alpha_0.$$

$\tanh(U_g)$ is the models prediction and m_g is the observed quantity which is the empirical average choice. Applying least squares method to the model which minimizes the square norm of the difference between the observed and predicted quantities. But the observed quantity in our case is the same as the empirical average choice m_g . Therefore we need to find the parameter values which minimizes

$$\sum_g [\bar{m}_g - \tanh(U_g)]^2$$

The function $\tanh(U_g)$ is non-linear and will make computations very cumbersome. This problem has already been encountered by Berkson back in the nineteen-fifties, when developing a statistical methodology for bioassay [25]: this is an interesting point, since this stimulus-response kind of experiment bears a close analogy to the natural kind of applications for a model of social behaviour, such as linking stimula given by incentive through policy and media, to behaviour responses on the part of individuals in a population. Furthermore the same approach is used by statistical mechanics,

for example within the problem of finding the proper order parameter for a given Hamiltonian [22]. Since U_g is a linear function of the models parameters, and \tanh is an invertible function the above error estimation is reduced to the following

$$\sum_g [\operatorname{arctanh}(m_g) - U_g]^2. \quad (2.12)$$

The method breaks down when the average opinion m_g of a group is equivalent to $+1$ or -1 , i.e. ($m_g \equiv \pm 1$), since $\operatorname{arctanh}(m_g) = \pm\infty$ then if the size of the groups is large enough $m_g = \pm 1$ will not occur. From equation (2.12) we will rewrite U_g as,

$$U_g = J_{g1}\bar{m}_1 + J_{g2}\bar{m}_2 + J_{g3}\bar{m}_3 + J_{g4}\bar{m}_4 + \alpha_1 a_g^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_g^{(2)} + \alpha_0$$

for $g = 1, \dots, 4$ and expanding it further we get

$$U_1 = J_{11}\bar{m}_1 + J_{12}\bar{m}_2 + J_{13}\bar{m}_3 + J_{14}\bar{m}_4 + J_{21} \cdot 0 + J_{22} \cdot 0 + J_{23} \cdot 0 + J_{24} \cdot 0 + J_{31} \cdot 0 + J_{32} \cdot 0 + J_{33} \cdot 0 + J_{34} \cdot 0 + J_{41} \cdot 0 + J_{42} \cdot 0 + J_{43} \cdot 0 + J_{44} \cdot 0 + \alpha_1 a_1^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_1^{(2)} + \alpha_0,$$

$$U_2 = J_{11} \cdot 0 + J_{12} \cdot 0 + J_{13} \cdot 0 + J_{14} \cdot 0 + J_{21}\bar{m}_1 + J_{22}\bar{m}_2 + J_{23}\bar{m}_3 + J_{24}\bar{m}_4 + J_{31} \cdot 0 + J_{32} \cdot 0 + J_{33} \cdot 0 + J_{34} \cdot 0 + J_{41} \cdot 0 + J_{42} \cdot 0 + J_{43} \cdot 0 + J_{44} \cdot 0 + \alpha_1 a_2^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_2^{(2)} + \alpha_0,$$

$$U_3 = J_{11} \cdot 0 + J_{12} \cdot 0 + J_{13} \cdot 0 + J_{14} \cdot 0 + J_{21} \cdot 0 + J_{22} \cdot 0 + J_{23} \cdot 0 + J_{24} \cdot 0 + J_{31}\bar{m}_1 + J_{32}\bar{m}_2 + J_{33}\bar{m}_3 + J_{34}\bar{m}_4 + \bar{J}_{41} \cdot 0 + \bar{J}_{42} \cdot 0 + \bar{J}_{43} \cdot 0 + J_{44} \cdot 0 + \alpha_1 a_3^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_3^{(2)} + \alpha_0,$$

$$U_4 = J_{11} \cdot 0 + J_{12} \cdot 0 + J_{13} \cdot 0 + J_{14} \cdot 0 + J_{21} \cdot 0 + J_{22} \cdot 0 + J_{23} \cdot 0 + J_{24} \cdot 0 + J_{31} \cdot 0 + J_{32} \cdot 0 + J_{33} \cdot 0 + J_{34} \cdot 0 + J_{41}\bar{m}_1 + J_{42}\bar{m}_2 + J_{43}\bar{m}_3 + J_{44}\bar{m}_4 + \alpha_1 a_4^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_4^{(2)} + \alpha_0.$$

Our model is now a system of linear equations and can be written in the form of

$$U = MX \tag{2.13}$$

where U is a 4×1 matrix which is known to be the tangent hyperbolic inverse of the equilibrium state \bar{m}_g , M is a 4×19 matrix with number of columns greater than number of rows and X represent the vector of the model's parameters.

Definition 2.3.1.

$M^T M X = M^T U$ is called the normal equation associated with the least squares problem.

If $M^T M$ has an inverse, then the solution of the normal equation is also a solution of the least squares problem. Rearranging, we have $X = (M^T M)^{-1} M^T U$, the matrix $(M^T M)^{-1} M^T$ is the Moore-Penrose pseudo inverse of M (some-times just called the pseudo inverse) [26] and M^T is the transpose of the matrix M and $(M^T M)^{-1}$ is the inverse of $M^T M$. The procedure explained above is for the estimation of the interacting models parameters.

The matrices used are illustrated bellow;

$$X = \left[J_{11} \ J_{12} \ J_{13} \ J_{14} \ J_{21} \ J_{22} \ J_{23} \ J_{24} \ J_{31} \ J_{32} \ J_{33} \ J_{34} \ J_{41} \ J_{42} \ J_{43} \ J_{44} \ \alpha_1 \ \alpha_2 \ \alpha_0 \right]^T,$$

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} \tanh^{-1} \bar{m}_1 \\ \tanh^{-1} \bar{m}_2 \\ \tanh^{-1} \bar{m}_3 \\ \tanh^{-1} \bar{m}_4 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and}$$

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{m}_1 & \bar{m}_2 & \bar{m}_3 & \bar{m}_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{m}_1 & \bar{m}_2 & \bar{m}_3 & \bar{m}_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{m}_1 & \bar{m}_2 & \bar{m}_3 & \bar{m}_4 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{m}_1 & \bar{m}_2 & \bar{m}_3 & \bar{m}_4 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

where y^T means transpose of y .

For the non-interacting model we recall that $U_g = h_g$ and we will rewrite the equation for $g = 1, \dots, 4$ as follows;

$$U_1 = h_1 = \alpha_1 a_1^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_1^{(2)} + \alpha_0$$

$$U_2 = h_2 = \alpha_1 a_2^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_2^{(2)} + \alpha_0$$

$$U_3 = h_3 = \alpha_1 a_3^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_3^{(2)} + \alpha_0$$

$$U_4 = h_4 = \alpha_1 a_4^{(1)} + \alpha_2 a_4^{(2)} + \alpha_0$$

We now have a system of liner equations with three parameters or unknowns $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_0$. We can formalise it just as we had in the interacting model with the same procedure. Thus $U = AX$ where U is a 4×1 matrix and A is a 4×3 matrix and X represent the vector of the model's parameters of the non-interacting model.

Using the same concept as in the interacting model, the estimated parameter vector of the system becomes $X = (A^T A)^{-1} A^T U$ where A^T is the transpose of A and $(A^T A)^{-1}$ the inverse of $A^T A$. The matrices for the model are defined below;

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} \tanh^{-1} \bar{m}_1 \\ \tanh^{-1} \bar{m}_2 \\ \tan^{-1} \bar{m}_3 \\ \tan^{-1} \bar{m}_4 \end{bmatrix}, \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} a_1^{(1)} & a_1^{(2)} & 1 \\ a_2^{(1)} & a_2^{(2)} & 1 \\ a_3^{(1)} & a_3^{(2)} & 1 \\ a_4^{(1)} & a_4^{(2)} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad X = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We use MATLAB for our computations and the results will be shown in the next chapter.

Chapter 3

Case Study

We will consider real world problem and apply it to our estimation procedure for our model. The data was obtained from the 2014 Ghana Demographic and Health Survey (2014 GDHS) report carried out by the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS), Ghana Health Service (GHS) and the National Public Health Reference Laboratory (NPHRL) of the GHS. This report presents findings from the 2014 Ghana Demographic and Health Survey (GDHS), a nationally representative survey of 13,265 people age 15-49 and 10,474 people with age 15-49 for educational and employment choices respectively from 11,835 interviewed households of which we see as an ideal testing ground for our model.

Individuals in this report are assigned to their socio-economic attributes such as place of residence (rural or urban) and gender (male or female). The attributes are assigned to the groups the individuals belong to since a group is made up of individuals characterised by the same socio-economic attribute. In what follows we will consider the following choices for our socio-economic attributes.

Cases	Attribute			
	Gender ($a_g^{(1)}$)		Residence ($a_g^{(2)}$)	
	Male	Female	Urban	Rural
1	0	1	1	0
2	1	0	0	1
3	0	1	0	1
4	1	0	1	0

Table 1: Socio-Economic Attributes for Individuals.

Note that if $a_g^{(1)} = 0$, then it means that that attribute has no effect of the private incentive of the group. In what follows we will analyse all the above four cases to the effect of having no private incentive on the social interaction strength $J_{gg'}$. In the sequel we will employ the above estimation procedure and the parametrisation of the attributes to study educational and occupational choices made by the people in Ghana.

3.1 Educational Attainment

Concerning the first task we use data coming from a report compiled by Ghana Demographic and Health Survey in the year 2014. This survey consist of a population of over 13 thousand people coming from across the country, involving both rural and urban areas and has information on gender.

With this particular sample size of 13 thousand we will escape the problem concerning sample size as explained in the previous section under estimation. Here we are looking at groups of individuals that have been partitioned according to these two

binary attribute $a_g^{(1)}$ and $a_g^{(2)}$ representing gender and residence respectively. We would want to investigate how residence, gender and once social environment influence his/her choice of educational attainment.

The table below shows the partitioning of the population on educational attainment with respect to their socio-economic attributes.

	Urban	Rural
Male	2050	1819
Female	5051	4345

Table 2: Groupings of the population according to attributes.

With this kind of partitioning we will get four groups indexed by $g = 1, \dots, 4$. In particular,

- $g = 1$ represent males in urban group
- $g = 2$ represent males in rural group
- $g = 3$ represent females in urban group
- $g = 4$ represent females in rural group

Under this case study we will be looking at individuals deciding on having education below Senior High School (SHS) which includes Junior High School, Primary and no education versus having SHS and above education. With this we will formalise σ_i as

$$\sigma_i = \begin{cases} +1, & \text{if individual } i \text{ has SHS and above education} \\ -1, & \text{if individual } i \text{ has below SHS education} \end{cases}$$

With this realisation, we will regroup our population depending on the choices made by individuals and also consider their attributes.

	Urban	Rural
Male	1783	1181
Female	3793	2133

Table 3: Educational Attainment: Senior High School and above.

	Urban	Rural
Male	267	638
Female	1258	2212

Table 4: Educational Attainment: Below Senior High School.

From Tables 3 and 4 we will derive our weighted averages for the various groups. We recall that the weighted average is $m_g = \frac{N_g}{N} \hat{m}_g$ and if $\hat{m}_g = \frac{1}{N_g} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i$ is substituted into it we get that

$$m_g = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i = \frac{1}{N} \left(N_{SHS_{\geq}}^g - N_{SHS_{<}}^g \right), \quad (3.1)$$

where $N_{SHS_{\geq}}^g$ is the number of people in group g with SHS and above education and $N_{SHS_{<}}^g$ is the number of individuals in group g with below SHS education, for g running from 1 to 4.

When:

$g = 1$: Male in Urban

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= \frac{1}{13265} \cdot (1783 - 267) \\ &= \frac{4}{35} \end{aligned}$$

$g = 2$: Male in Rural

$$m_2 = \frac{1}{13265} \cdot (1181 - 638)$$

$$= \frac{543}{13265}$$

$g = 3$: Female in Urban

$$m_3 = \frac{1}{13265} \cdot (3793 - 1258)$$

$$= \frac{507}{2653}$$

$g = 4$: Female in Rural

$$m_4 = \frac{1}{13265} \cdot (2133 - 2212)$$

$$= \frac{-79}{13265}$$

We will now compute the values of the attributes $a_g^{(1)}$ and $a_g^{(2)}$ for gender and residence respectively, depending on the group an individual belongs, for the four cases generated in Table 1 above. For these values of the attributes see Table 2. The values assigned to the attributes in each of the four cases describe the relevance of that attribute to the private incentive part of the Hamiltonian. For instance in Case 1 being a male as an attribute does not contribute to the private incentive of a group whiles being a female contributes and being in a rural area does not contribute to the private incentive of a group whiles being in the urban area contribute to the private incentive of a group.

Cases	Group Attributes							
	$a_1^{(1)}$	$a_1^{(2)}$	$a_2^{(1)}$	$a_2^{(2)}$	$a_3^{(1)}$	$a_3^{(2)}$	$a_4^{(1)}$	$a_4^{(2)}$
1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
2	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1
3	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
4	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0

Table 5: Socio-Economic Attributes for Groups.

With this we can easily generate our matrices for the various models.

The result of the estimation for the inter and intra-group coupling strength for educational attainment and its attributes are shown below. Table 6, shows the estimates for non-interacting discrete choice model whereas Table 7 present the estimates for the interacting model's parameters, for all the case in Table 1 and 5.

Parameters	Confidence Interval For:			
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
α_1	0.016 ± 1.84	-0.016 ± 1.84	0.016 ± 1.84	0.016 ± 1.84
α_2	0.137 ± 1.84	-0.137 ± 1.84	-0.137 ± 1.84	0.137 ± 1.84
α_0	0.010 ± 1.60	0.162 ± 1.60	0.162 ± 1.60	0.010 ± 1.60

Table 6: Educational Attainment: Estimation for the non-interacting model.

	Confidence Interval For:			
Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
\hat{J}_{11}	-0.462 ± 0.47	0.027 ± 0.13	-0.364 ± 0.06	-0.009 ± 0.06
\hat{J}_{12}	0.061 ± 0.28	0.0353 ± 0.29	3.829 ± 0.25	-0.12 ± 0.34
\hat{J}_{13}	0.052 ± 0.05	0.0002 ± 0.00	-1.548 ± 0.03	0.0001 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{14}	1.607 ± 1.81	0.545 ± 3.02	16.424 ± 1.83	-0.018 ± 3.24
\hat{J}_{21}	-0.036 ± 0.10	-0.008 ± 0.05	0.368 ± 0.08	0.002 ± 0.03
\hat{J}_{22}	-0.003 ± 0.06	-0.023 ± 0.33	-5.325 ± 0.22	-0.030 ± 0.36
\hat{J}_{23}	-0.027 ± 0.08	0.001 ± 0.00	1.451 ± 0.05	-0.0003 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{24}	-0.051 ± 0.26	-1.218 ± 3.94	29.010 ± 1.91	1.170 ± 3.47
\hat{J}_{31}	0.111 ± 0.30	-0.009 ± 0.03	0.617 ± 0.05	0.0004 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{32}	0.056 ± 0.30	0.024 ± 0.05	-1.554 ± 0.22	0.004 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{33}	-0.001 ± 0.00	-0.004 ± 0.02	0.327 ± 0.05	0.0004 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{34}	-3.920 ± 4.45	-0.011 ± 0.35	39.104 ± 2.52	-0.055 ± 0.28
\hat{J}_{41}	-0.001 ± 0.01	0.001 ± 0.03	-0.253 ± 0.03	0.003 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{42}	0.228 ± 0.28	0.002 ± 0.06	1.52 ± 0.24	0.005 ± 0.03
\hat{J}_{43}	0.020 ± 0.03	0.001 ± 0.02	-0.954 ± 0.05	-0.001 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{44}	2.547 ± 2.33	0.023 ± 0.89	-5.671 ± 2.48	0.007 ± 0.00
$\hat{\alpha}_1$	0.005 ± 0.01	0.022 ± 0.04	0.111 ± 0.02	0.006 ± 0.04
$\hat{\alpha}_2$	0.125 ± 0.07	-0.001 ± 0.00	-0.742 ± 0.02	-0.001 ± 0.00
$\hat{\alpha}_0$	-0.002 ± 0.01	-0.0001 ± 0.00	0.127 ± 0.10	-0.0002 ± 0.00

Table 7: Educational Attainment: Estimation for the interacting model.

3.2 Employment Choices

Our second case study uses data coming from the report compiled by Ghana Demographic and Health Survey in the year 2014. This report contains information on occupational choices in the various sectors of work. We will focus on sales and services as one category of occupation and combine all other aspects of occupation as another employment option. This leads to a binary choice scenario where individuals either being a female or a male and living in an urban or a rural area chooses between sales and services and the other type of work options. The table below shows the partitioning of the population on occupational choice with respect to their socio-economic attributes.

	Urban	Rural
Male	1679	1601
Female	3871	3323

Table 8: Groupings of the population according to attributes.

Here we are looking at individuals being partitioned into groups based on their attributes $a^{(1)}$ and $a^{(2)}$ representing gender and residence respectively.

This produces four groups in the same manner as found under Section 3.1 on educational attainment. We will be focusing on individuals choosing sales and services and others as an alternate option of employment.

With this we will formalise σ_i as follows:

$$\sigma_i = \begin{cases} +1, & \text{if individual } i \text{ choses sales and services} \\ -1, & \text{if individual } i \text{ choses from others} \end{cases}$$

With this realisation, we will regroup our population depending on their employment choices and socio-economic attributes.

	Urban	Rural
Male	353	112
Female	2477	1163

Table 9: Occupational Choices: Sales and Services

	Urban	Rural
Male	1326	1489
Female	1394	2160

Table 10: Occupational Choices: Others

Table 9 and Table 10 shows the share of individuals choosing to work at the sales and services sector and any other working sector. From Tables 9 and 10 we will derive our weighted averages for the various groups. We recall that the weighted average is $m_g = \frac{N_g}{N} \hat{m}_g$ and if $\hat{m}_g = \frac{1}{N_g} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i$ is substituted into it, we get

$$m_g = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i \in I_{N_g}} \sigma_i = \frac{1}{N} (N_{SS}^g - N_{OT}^g), \quad (3.2)$$

where N_{SS}^g is the number of people in group g who are into sales and services and N_{OT}^g is the number of people in group g who are into the other employment sectors.

When:

$g = 1$: Male in Urban

$$\begin{aligned} m_1 &= \frac{1}{10474} \cdot (353 - 1326) \\ &= \frac{-973}{10474} \end{aligned}$$

$g = 2$: Male in Rural

$$m_2 = \frac{1}{10474} \cdot (112 - 1489)$$

$$= \frac{-1377}{10474}$$

$g = 3$: Female in Urban

$$m_3 = \frac{1}{10474} \cdot (2477 - 1394)$$

$$= \frac{1083}{10474}$$

$g = 4$: Female in Rural

$$m_4 = \frac{1}{10474} \cdot (1163 - 2160)$$

$$= \frac{-997}{10474}$$

The computations and values for the attribute $a_g^{(1)}$ and $a_g^{(2)}$ for gender and residence respectively are the same as in Tables 1 and 5 of Section 3.1.

Table 11 presents the estimates for the parameters of our non-interacting models while Table 12 contains information on the estimates for the corresponding interacting discrete choice model.

	Confidence Interval For:			
Parameters	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
$\hat{\alpha}_1$	0.117 ± 1.91	-0.117 ± 1.91	0.117 ± 1.91	-0.117 ± 1.91
$\hat{\alpha}_2$	0.119 ± 1.91	-0.119 ± 1.91	-0.119 ± 1.91	0.119 ± 1.91
$\hat{\alpha}_0$	-0.172 ± 1.66	0.064 ± 1.66	-0.053 ± 1.66	-0.055 ± 1.66

Table 11: Employment Choices: Estimation for the non-interacting model.

	Confidence Interval For:			
Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
\hat{J}_{11}	0.669 ± 1.35	7.212 ± 1.47	-1.661 ± 2.19	2.847 ± 1.47
\hat{J}_{12}	-1.068 ± 0.39	1.203 ± 0.20	-4.234 ± 1.50	1.804 ± 0.17
\hat{J}_{13}	-2.910 ± 1.15	7.426 ± 0.88	-4.078 ± 1.19	-12.48 ± 0.80
\hat{J}_{14}	0.456 ± 1.74	-3.92 ± 3.43	2.773 ± 2.21	-6.055 ± 3.71
\hat{J}_{21}	3.152 ± 0.74	-0.662 ± 0.91	0.122 ± 2.54	1.763 ± 0.75
\hat{J}_{22}	-0.430 ± 1.36	-2.896 ± 0.32	-4.332 ± 1.50	-3.103 ± 0.46
\hat{J}_{23}	0.052 ± 0.53	2.998 ± 0.00	-0.16 ± 0.92	9.424 ± 0.00
\hat{J}_{24}	-0.265 ± 0.32	-4.477 ± 4.09	-0.085 ± 1.50	-2.84 ± 4.16
\hat{J}_{31}	-0.055 ± 0.84	0.210 ± 0.94	3.478 ± 2.54	1.317 ± 0.17
\hat{J}_{32}	0.382 ± 0.49	-1.435 ± 1.34	-0.974 ± 1.50	3.236 ± 0.43
\hat{J}_{33}	4.836 ± 0.01	0.586 ± 0.88	-0.974 ± 0.92	5.325 ± 0.66
\hat{J}_{34}	-2.606 ± 3.26	-0.245 ± 0.26	-2.858 ± 1.50	-0.484 ± 0.31
\hat{J}_{41}	0.048 ± 0.46	-1.787 ± 0.15	-0.987 ± 2.54	-4.751 ± 0.91
\hat{J}_{42}	0.759 ± 0.39	-3.279 ± 0.44	0.862 ± 1.50	0.932 ± 1.30
\hat{J}_{43}	1.158 ± 0.31	-0.426 ± 0.62	-3.104 ± 0.92	2.481 ± 0.92
\hat{J}_{44}	0.661 ± 1.52	1.448 ± 0.34	0.138 ± 1.50	2.039 ± 0.29
$\hat{\alpha}_1$	-0.100 ± 0.16	-0.394 ± 0.14	-0.564 ± 0.33	-0.181 ± 0.45
$\hat{\alpha}_2$	-0.755 ± 0.30	-0.538 ± 0.15	-0.062 ± 0.33	0.199 ± 0.15
$\hat{\alpha}_0$	0.163 ± 0.12	0.404 ± 0.13	0.00 ± 0.22	0.134 ± 0.12

Table 12: Employment Choices: Estimation for the interacting model.

Chapter 4

Discussion and Conclusion

4.1 Educational Attainment

We will begin by considering the estimates for the non-interacting model then followed by the interacting model.

4.1.1 Non-interacting Case

When the sum of the $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s of the private incentive of a group is a positive value then that group will make a choice favouring SHS and above education and when the sum is a negative value then the group will make a choice favouring below SHS education.

The estimates of the private incentive for gender $\hat{\alpha}_1$ is very small and closer to zero for all the four cases considered. Implying ones gender does not really contribute to the private incentive of an individual towards obtaining educational attainment when there is no interaction present.

For the estimate of the private incentive for residence $\hat{\alpha}_2$, Cases 2 and 3 has the same negative value. In Cases 2 and 3 being in the urban area does not contribute to the private incentive of a group. So the negative value implies individuals in the rural

area will prefer to obtain educational level below SHS. Whiles for Cases 1 and 4 we have a positive value, telling us that individuals in the urban areas will choose SHS and above education. In these groups being in the rural does not contribute to the private incentive of that group. This indicates that the residence of an individual has effect or is a major deterministic factor on the choices Ghanaians make towards educational attainment.

The base private incentive $\hat{\alpha}_0$, has a positive value for all the cases. Cases 1 and 4 have a value closer to zero, which means that in a situation where interaction is absent individuals considered in these cases will rely on their gender or residence to make a choice. But looking at Cases 2 and 3 they have a bigger positive values for $\hat{\alpha}_0$, which is the biggest of all the estimates that have been obtained for non-interacting model. These estimates for α_0 in Cases 2 and 3 signifies that individuals will prefer a choice relating to SHS and above education.

4.1.2 Interacting Case

Considering the interacting model which is made up of the social and private incentives for each group in a population. Whenever the coefficient of the social incentive $\hat{J}_{gg'}$ of groups g and g' is positive then it means individuals in groups g and g' prefer to imitate themselves or conformity is rewarded. Whiles when $\hat{J}_{gg'}$ is negative, then groups g and g' will prefer different choices. Thus conformity or imitation is not rewarded. When the $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s of the private incentive of a group sum up to give a positive value then at the private level individuals in that group will make a choice favouring SHS and above education and when it sums up to a negative value then individuals in the group will make a choice favouring below SHS education.

Consider \hat{J}_{11} (the interaction strength of males in urban area interacting with males in urban area) of Table 7. In Case 1 being a male does not contributes to the private

incentives of the groups but living in the urban area contributes to the private incentives of the groups. Hence males in urban do not care about other males choices towards education. Therefore they do not imitate themselves. In Case 2 being a male is important and contributes to the private incentives of the groups whiles living in the urban area does not. Hence individuals will like to imitate or conform with other individuals choices. For Case 3, being a male and living in the urban does not contribute to the private incentives of the groups. Therefore individuals do not care and do not conform with each other, because both gender and residence does not contribute to their private incentive. Being a male and living the urban area contribute to the private incentives of the groups in Case 4. For Case 4, \hat{J}_{11} has a negative estimate and close to zero, which implies conformity in that group interaction is not rewarded.

Next we will consider \hat{J}_{14} (which is the influence males in urban area has on females in the rural area) of Table 7. In Case 1 being a male does not contribute to the private incentives of the groups whiles being a female does and also living in the urban area has effect on the private incentives of the groups whiles living the rural area has no effect on the private incentives of the groups. With this we had a positive estimate indicating that males in the urban areas can influence females in the rural areas. Here conformity or imitation is rewarded. For Case 2 being a male and living in the rural area has effect on the private incentives of the groups whiles being a female and living in the urban area has no effect on the private incentives of the groups. This also yielded a positive estimate indicating that conformity is rewarded. Case 3 also has a positive estimate which means imitation or conformity is rewarded.

But Case 4, where being a male and living in the urban area contributes to the private incentives of the groups whiles being a female and living in the rural area does not contribute to the private incentives of the groups has a negative estimate. This implies conformity or imitation is not rewarded. This is because males in urban area

are influencing females in the rural area but being a female and living in the rural area does not contribute to their private incentives.

According to the estimate for J_{14} , when policy makers in Ghana want to increase literacy or push more females into higher educational levels they should consider using males in the urban areas with a higher educational attainment provided being a female in rural area is considered.

At the private level considering $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s, the groups in Case 1 will make a choice favouring SHS and above education which is the same for all the cases except for Case 3 because the sum of the $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s is negative implying groups will make a choice favouring below SHS education.

4.2 Employment Choices

The estimates for the non-interacting model will be discussed first followed by the interacting model.

4.2.1 Non-interacting Case

If the sum of the $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s of the private incentive of a group has a positive value then the group will make a choice favouring sales and service and when the sum is a negative value then the group will make a choice favouring others as their employment choice.

For Cases 1 and 3 the sum of the $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s gives a positive value, which imply individuals considered in these cases will prefer sales and services as their employment choice. In Cases 2 and 4 the sum of the $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s in each cases have a negative value implying individuals in each of the cases will choose others as their employment choice when interaction is absent.

Cases 1, 3 and 4 have a negative base private incentive $\hat{\alpha}_0$ indicating that when the

socio-economic attributes gender and residence are not considered individuals in these cases will choose others as their employment choice. Whiles individuals in Case 2 will choose sales and services when gender and residence are not considered. This is because the base private incentive $\hat{\alpha}_0$ for Case 2 is positive.

4.2.2 Interacting Case

Whenever the coefficient of the social incentive $\hat{J}_{gg'}$ of groups g and g' is positive then individuals in groups g and g' prefer to imitate themselves. Whiles when $\hat{J}_{gg'}$ is negative, groups g and g' will make a choice that differ from each other. Thus conformity or imitation is not rewarded between groups g and g' . When the $\hat{\alpha}_j$'s of the private incentive of a group sum up to give a positive value then at the private level individuals will prefer a choice favouring sales and services and when it sums up to a negative value then the individuals will prefer a choice favouring others as their employment choice.

We will now consider the estimate for J_{33} (the interaction strength for females in urban area interacting with themselves) in Table 12. For Case 1, being a female and living in the urban area has effect on the private incentives of the groups, and the estimate for J_{33} is a positive value. This indicates that there is conformity as females in urban area interact with themselves in making choices towards employment when being a female and living in the urban area has effect on their private incentive. In Case 2, we have that being a female and living in the urban area has no effect on the private incentives of the groups. For Case 2, \hat{J}_{33} has a positive value which indicates that there is conformity when females in the urban area influence themselves. Concerning Case 3, being a female has effect on the private incentives of the groups but living in the urban has no effect on the private incentives of the groups. J_{33} has a negative estimate for Case 3 and indicates that imitation is not rewarded. Whiles for Case 4, \hat{J}_{33} has

a positive value indicating that conformity is rewarded whenever being a female does not contribute to the private incentives of groups whereas living in the urban area contribute to the private incentives of groups.

Next we consider the influence females in urban areas have on females in rural areas \hat{J}_{34} found in Table 12. The estimate for J_{34} in all the four cases are negative which implies imitation is not rewarded for the interaction between females in the urban area and females in rural area. \hat{J}_{44} in Table 12, has positive value for all the cases considered. This indicates that conformity or imitation is rewarded for the interaction between females in rural.

4.3 Open Problems

It is worthwhile to mention some possible extensions and generalizations of the current study. Among these are

1. Consideration of general functional forms of the attributes functions. Recall that the four cases considered in Tables 1 and 5 corresponds to different choices for the functional form of the attributes. As a follow up to this work we will consider general functional form for the attributes that combines all the four functional forms of the attribute functions.
2. Consideration of attributes with more than two attribute alternatives, for example residence could have the alternatives of village, town and city.
3. Consideration of choice problems that are not binary. Here the Potts model will be ideal for the study.

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